

FINITE STRAIN PARAMETRIC HFGMC PREDICTION OF THE MICROMECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF COMPOSITE

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Keywords: Micromechanics, Finite strain, Composite, Computational mechanics

ABSTRACT

Finite-strain mechanical behavior of composite materials is of great interest. For example, composite such as reinforced rubber and soft tissues can reach more than 200% of stretch, and therefore a suitable micromechanical analysis tool must be used for the prediction. In order to predict the micro- and macro-scale behavior of these composites, the Parametric High-Fidelity-Generalized-Method-of-Cells (P-HFGMC) that has been established for infinitesimal strains is now extended to incorporate for the finite-strain micromechanical analysis of composites. The P-HFGMC is a micromechanical analysis that based on the homogenization technique for periodic materials and provides the global (homogenized-field) response, the local (fluctuation-field) tensor field distributions, and the instantaneous stiffness matrix of the composite. Predictions of the transverse uniaxial tensile-stress-state response, as well as the response to an equally-biaxial compressive deformation-gradient state, of unidirectional composites (UDs) with potential-based energy functions constituents such as the compressible Mooney-Rivlin model (MR) are demonstrated. Both the macroscale (global) transverse first Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor – deformation gradient response, as well as the tensors distribution (local) within the constituents, are presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

Finite-strain mechanical behavior of composites such as fiber-reinforced rubbers and biological tissues is of great interest. Prediction of the structural and material homogenized elastic response of such materials has been a major challenge for hyperelastic phases. One approach to describe the finite-strain mechanical behavior of composites is to employ closed-form analytical models such as the anisotropic material representation proposed by Holzapfel [1] among others.

An alternative approach, which is adopted in this paper is to model the true structure of the composite and the constitutive equation of each phase, in conjunction with an appropriate micromechanical model, in order to obtain the effective homogenized response of the composite.

In the present investigation, the proposed model is the high-fidelity-generalized-method-of-cells (HFGMC) that has previously been employed for infinitesimal-strain mechanical behavior of composite, see [2] for extensive capabilities of the method. The discussed HFGMC is based on orthogonal discretization and has been used to capture the finite-strain mechanical response of composites [3], the buckling and postbuckling prediction of layered composites [4], the failure prediction of unidirectional composites [5] and more. Presently, the parametric HFGMC that has been proposed by [6] is generalized for the analysis of finite-strain hyperelastic composites. This generalization improves the capability of the HFGMC model in its ability to capture the given geometry of the constituents of the composite with a minimum number of subcells.

The proposed finite-strain parametric HFGMC model is implemented on several hyperelastic constituents to produce the results of the micro-fields distribution. In addition, the predicted effective behavior is compared to finite-element-analysis (FEA) results.

2 FINITE STRAIN IMPLEMENTATION WITHIN THE PARAMETRIC HFGMC

In the present investigation composites which are characterized by a doubly-periodic microstructure are investigated. Hence, a repeating-unit-cell (RUC) can be identified and analyzed as seen in Fig.1.

Figure 1: Schematic drawing of a composite with repeating geometrical pattern (a), Doubly-periodic RUC (b), subcell mesh (c), Parametric coordinates and geometry (d), and Physical coordinates and geometry (e).

In the framework of the parametric HFGMC methodology, the incremental displacement field can be described as,

$$\Delta \mathbf{u}^{(\beta)} = \Delta \mathbf{u}^0 + \Delta \mathbf{w}_0^{(\beta)} + \frac{1}{2} (\Delta \mathbf{w}_2^{(\beta)} - \Delta \mathbf{w}_4^{(\beta)}) r_2 + \frac{1}{2} (\Delta \mathbf{w}_3^{(\beta)} - \Delta \mathbf{w}_1^{(\beta)}) r_3 + \frac{1}{4} (\Delta \mathbf{w}_2^{(\beta)} + \Delta \mathbf{w}_4^{(\beta)} - 2\Delta \mathbf{w}_0^{(\beta)}) (3r_2^2 + r_2 r_3 - 1) + \frac{1}{4} (\Delta \mathbf{w}_1^{(\beta)} + \Delta \mathbf{w}_3^{(\beta)} - 2\Delta \mathbf{w}_0^{(\beta)}) (3r_3^2 + r_2 r_3 - 1) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{w}_i^{(\beta)}$ are the unknown microvariables, r and s , are the Cartesian in-plane coordinates of the subcell in the parametric domain, and \mathbf{u}^0 are the homogenized-field displacement. Hence, the incremental deformation gradient tensor of each subcell is expressed by,

$$\Delta \mathbf{F}^{(\beta)} = \Delta \mathbf{F}^0 + \mathbf{A}_w^{(\beta)} \Delta \mathbf{w}^{(\beta)} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{A}_{w,ij}^{(\beta)}$ relates the microvariables to the deformation gradient to provide the fluctuation-field reaction to the macro-field incremental displacement. The stress measure used in this numerical scheme is the first Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor, which can be related to the deformation gradient through the forth-order instantaneous stiffness matrix as,

$$\Delta \mathbf{T}^{(\beta)} = \mathbf{R}^{(\beta)} \Delta \mathbf{F}^{(\beta)} \quad (3)$$

As first suggested in [6] for infinitesimal-strain, a two-scaled virtual-work-balance principle is employed for each subcell as,

$$\delta \mathbf{F}^{0,T} \mathbf{I}_{F^0}^{(\beta)} + \delta \mathbf{w}^{(\beta),T} \mathbf{I}_w^{(\beta)} = \int_{V^{(\beta)}} \delta \mathbf{F}^{(\beta),T} \mathbf{T}^{(\beta)} dV \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{I}_{F^0}^{(\beta)}$, $\mathbf{I}_w^{(\beta)}$ are the macroscale and microscale internal resisting vector, respectively, and can be expressed for each subcell by,

$$\mathbf{I}_{\mathbf{F}^0}^{(\beta)} = \int_{V^{(\beta)}} \mathbf{T}^{(\beta)} dV, \quad \mathbf{I}_{\mathbf{w}}^{(\beta)} = \int_{V^{(\beta)}} \mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{w}}^{(\beta)} \mathbf{T}^{(\beta)} dV \quad (5)$$

Equilibrium of the whole RUC is achieved in a two-scale level manner where the internal resisting vectors are balanced by the homogenized-field force, $\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{F}^0}$, and the fluctuation-filed force, $\mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{w}}$ by,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{w}} \\ \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{F}^0} \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{\mathbf{w}} \\ \mathbf{I}_{\mathbf{F}^0} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where for a nonlinear micromechanical analysis, satisfying Eq. (6) is difficult to achieve in an exact manner. Therefore, a numerical routine must be employed where a residual vector, \mathbf{R} , is being defined as,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{w}}^{\text{es}} \\ \mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{F}^0}^{\text{es}} \end{Bmatrix} \equiv \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{w}} \\ \mathbf{P}_{\mathbf{F}^0} \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{\mathbf{w}} \\ \mathbf{I}_{\mathbf{F}^0} \end{Bmatrix} \approx \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

In incremental-scheme solutions, one can use the first-order term of the Taylor expansion in order to linearize the set of micromechanical equations. For a general increment, n , the residual will be evaluated as,

$$\mathbf{R}^{\text{es}}|_{(\mathbf{w}_n, \mathbf{F}_n^0)} \approx \mathbf{R}^{\text{es}}|_{(\mathbf{w}_{n-1}, \mathbf{F}_{n-1}^0)} + \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^{\text{es}}}{\partial \mathbf{w}} \right|_{(\mathbf{w}_{n-1}, \mathbf{F}_{n-1}^0)} \Delta \mathbf{w} + \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}^{\text{es}}}{\partial \mathbf{F}^0} \right|_{(\mathbf{w}_{n-1}, \mathbf{F}_{n-1}^0)} \Delta \mathbf{F}^0 \quad (8)$$

such that the derivatives of the residual define the ‘virtual-stiffness’ matrices of each subcell. Assembly of these contributions produce the global incremental set of equations as,

$$\begin{bmatrix} \int_V \mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{w}}^T \mathbf{R} \mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{w}} dV & \int_V \mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{w}}^T \mathbf{R} dV \\ \int_V \mathbf{R} \mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{w}} dV & \int_V \mathbf{R} dV \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta \mathbf{w} \\ \Delta \mathbf{F}^0 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

The solution of Eq. (7) is used to update the total values of the deformation-gradient and the first-Piola-Kirchhoff of the homogenized-field and the fluctuation-field, as well as the effective instantiates stiffness matrix of the whole RUC.

3 RESULTS

Results for a unidirectional composite with 5% and 25% fiber-volume-fraction (FVF) are presented. Subcell discretization for both RUCs parametric arrays is presented in Fig.2, where the fiber region is the round-green section in the middle of the square-array RUC. Constitutive material models chosen for this example are a linear isotropic elastic fiber and a hyperelastic compressible Mooney-Rivlin (MR) matrix-media where the mechanical properties of the constituents are written in Table 1, and the energy function of the matrix media is characterized by

$$W = C_{10}(\bar{I}_1 - 3) + C_{01}(\bar{I}_2 - 3) + \kappa/2 (J - 1)^2 \quad (10)$$

where C_{10} , C_{01} and κ are material properties, \bar{I}_1 and \bar{I}_2 are the reduced first and second invariants of the right Cauchy-Green deformation tensor defined by,

$$\bar{I}_1 = I_1 I_1^{-1/3}, \quad \bar{I}_2 = I_2 I_3^{-2/3} \quad (11)$$

and J is the square-root of the right Cauchy-Green deformation tensor’s third invariant. The first example presented herein is composite subjected to a macroscale transverse tension (in the Y_2 direction), such that $T_{22}^0 \neq 0$ and all other components are zero. The fluctuation-filed transverse stress distribution for the 5% case and the homogenized-field response of the composite with a comparison to finite-element-analysis (FEA) are presented in Fig.3 (a) and (b) respectively.

Figure 2: Square-array RUC with 1180 subcells and 1215 nodes of a 25% fiber-volume-fraction, and 816 subcells and 857 nodes of a 5% fiber-volume-fraction unidirectional composite.

For the second example, the 25% FVF is loaded in an equally-biaxial compressive deformation-gradient state where $F_{22}^0 = F_{33}^0 \neq 0$, and all of the other component values are zero, as seen in Fig.4. In-plane stress distribution in terms of the transverse first Piola-Kirchhoff, $T_{22}^{(\beta)}$, $T_{33}^{(\beta)}$, and the in-plan shear first Piola-Kirchhoff $T_{23}^{(\beta)}$, at $F_{22}^0 = F_{33}^0 = 0.875, 0.8125, 0.750$ as shown in Fig.5.

C_{10}^m (MPa)	C_{01}^m (MPa)	κ^m
0.3	0.1	3.0
E^f (MPa)	ν^f	
22.04	0.25	

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the constituents used for the example shown in Fig.2-4. m and f superscripts denote for matrix and fiber phase respectively.

Figure 3: Transverse First Piola-Kirchhoff stress, $T_{22}^{(\beta)}$, distribution at $F_{22}^0 = 1.15$ for the 5% FVF composite (a), and $T_{22}^0 - F_{22}^0$ response results for 5% and 25% FVF (b).

Figure 4: Equally-biaxial deformation-gradient load case of square-array RUC with 1180 subcells and 1215 nodes of a 25% fiber-volume-fraction.

Figure 5: In-plane first Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor field distribution results for the case of a 25% FVF unidirectional composites undergoing equally-biaxial transverse deformation gradient at $F_{22}^0 = F_{33}^0 = 0.875, 0.8125, 0.750$ presented in the left, middle and right columns, respectively.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The P-HFGMC has been extended for the finite-strain micromechanical analysis of composites. The ability of this method to create the stress-strain measures global response as well as local distribution has been demonstrated for both transverse uniaxial tensile stress state as well as equally-biaxial compressive deformation gradient state. For the first example, a good comparison with FEA results as well as with the orthogonal HFGMC has been shown. For the second example, the symmetry of macroscale description of the problem using an equally-biaxial deformation-gradient was highly pronounced in the local stress field results. Further research to improve convergence using incremental-iterative algorithm solution will be completed, as well as multiscale analysis of structure that undergoes finite-strain and extension for 3D RUCs will be performed.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported in part by a grant from the Pazy Foundation (No. 38932194) of the Israeli Council of Higher Education and the Israel Atomic Energy Commission. The last author gratefully acknowledges the support of the Nathan Cummings Chair in Mechanics.

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